

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF EPILEPSY IN THE FERGANA VALLEY

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Abstract. Epilepsy is diagnosed in 40-70 people per 100,000 in developed countries and in 100-190 people per 100,000 in developing countries annually, while in the Republic of Uzbekistan it is 87.2 per 100,000. The disease affects young, socially active part of society. These data emphasize the high medical, social and economic significance of the epilepsy problem in adults.

Key words: epilepsy, retrospective analysis, Fergana Valley, maladaptation

Purpose: To study epilepsy epidemiological characteristics in the Fergana Valley (based on register data).

Materials and Methods. A retrospective analysis of primary morbidity in the population of Fergana Valley for 2019-2020 was conducted. According to the register the prevalence of epilepsy among adults in Andijan per 1000 population was 2.7, in Fergana - 2.6, in Namangan - 1.8. The primary incidence and registered cases of epilepsy among adults in Andizhan per 100,000 inhabitants was 14.8, in Fergana 12.5 and in Namangan 12.3. The average age of patients in Namangan province was 41.4 ± 14.7 years, in Ferghana province 42.2 ± 14.2 years and in Andijan province 42.5 ± 14.3 years. The proportion of men examined in Namangan province was 60.5 per cent and 39.5 per cent for women. In the Ferghana region the proportion of male patients examined was 56 per cent and 44 per cent of female patients. In Andijan province, 53.2 per cent of male and 46.8 per cent of female patients were examined.

Results. In the surveyed population of Namangan province, 35.9% of patients had idiopathic generalized epilepsy, 30.8% had symptomatic epilepsy, and 33% had cryptogenic epilepsy. In Fergana oblast, 29.8% of patients had idiopathic generalized epilepsy, 28.7% had symptomatic epilepsy and 40.4% had cryptogenic epilepsy. In Andijan province, idiopathic generalized epilepsy was diagnosed in 23.1% of patients, symptomatic epilepsy in 35.1%, and cryptogenic epilepsy in 41.3%. The supposed etiological factors of epilepsy were: craniocerebral trauma (CMT) - 12.9% of cases (Andijan); cerebrovascular diseases - 13.1% (Namangan), 17% (Andijan); peri- and neonatal pathologies - 13.1% (Fergana).

The majority of patients were unemployed - 81.9%; 66.4% of patients received pensions, including disability pensions. 6.4% of patients were considered

socially active. On average, more than half of the patients in the study population, 66.5%, had a disability due to epilepsy. The disability group was 72.3% of patients. The majority of patients had group II disability - 36.8%. The high percentage of disability among patients in the Ferghana Valley indicates significant social and professional disadaptation of epilepsy patients due to disability.

Conclusions

1. The average annual incidence of epilepsy among adults in Andijan per 100,000 population was -14.8; in Ferghana - 12.5, in Namangan - 12.3. The prevalence of epilepsy in the Ferghana Valley (according to the register) was 2.7 people per 1000 population in Andijan province, 1.8 in Namangan province and 2.6 in Ferghana province.
2. Patients with idiopathic and cryptogenic epilepsy predominated in the studied population. The most frequent etiological factors were: craniocerebral trauma, cerebrovascular diseases, peri- and neonatal pathologies.
3. The assessment of the social status of patients with epilepsy revealed a predominance of unemployed persons. The proportion of socially active patients was 6.4%, and the disability rate was 72.3%, with a predominance of group 2 disabled.

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